

Accuracy Evaluation for Mental Health Indicator Based on Vocal Analysis in Noisy Environments

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Abstract: Mental health care is one of the important challenges in our modern stressful society. The authors proposed a method for measuring mental health based on the quality of the patient's voice, and implemented a system that monitors the state of mental health based on voice during a phone conversation via smartphone. However, there has been little consideration of the analysis of mental health using voices in a noisy environment thus far. Therefore, this study investigated the impact of noise on the mental health indicator based on vocal analysis. The results showed that the mental health level was judged to be low when the analyzed voice included noise. The study also revealed that a decreased precision in the detection of utterances had a significant impact on mental health analysis.

Keywords: Mental health care; noisy environment; vocal analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental health care has become increasingly important in modern times, in what is now considered a stressful society. Stress-induced mental disorders are now understood to cause significant losses for society [1], creating a need for technologies that can check the level of depression or stress in a simple manner to identify mental problems at an early stage.

Several methods have been developed for screening patients with mental health problems using a biomarker such as saliva [2], blood [3], heart rate [4], and electroencephalogram [5], but these methods are invasive and costly. Common non-invasive methods include self-descriptive psychological tests, such as the general health questionnaire (GHQ) [6] and Beck depression inventory (BDI) [7]. Self-descriptive psychological tests are relatively simple, but they cannot remove the influence of reporting bias. A reporting bias is a phenomenon in which specific information provided by the respondent is selectively over- or under-evaluated, either intentionally or unconsciously [8].

On the other hand, changes in mood are known by experience to manifest in the voice, and the authors have been working on the development of a method that estimates the mental health level, such as the state of depression or stress, based on the voice [9][10][11].

Vocal analysis is advantageous in that it is non-invasive, does not require specialized equipment, and can be performed easily and remotely. The authors focused on the voice in phone conversations and developed a monitoring system for mental health levels based on this voice, called the mind-monitoring system (MIMOSYS), by implementing this analytical approach on a widely adopted smartphone [12]. MIMOSYS is based on sensibility technology (ST) [13], and produces a value for "vitality," which quantifies the mental health level during the phone conversation based on the emotions analyzed by ST. A higher value for vitality represents a healthier mental state. The mental health level can be monitored by MIMOSYS on a daily basis to help prevent mental problems such as depression.

Although it would be ideal to eliminate noise from the voice data as much as possible in a vocal analysis, noise from the surrounding environment interferes in a hands-free phone conversation, and vitality may not be analyzed properly. An evaluation of the precision of vitality for voices under various noise environment showed that valid utterances were not detected for the vocal analysis, and judging whether a change in the vitality was due to the noise or due to a failure in detecting utterances proved to be difficult [14]. Therefore, an additional experiment was conducted in this study to investigate the impact of noise on vitality under an ideal utterance-detection condition.

II. METHODOLOGY

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A. Vocal analysis

ST used in MIMOSYS guesses the emotion of the speaker from a pattern in changes in the fundamental frequency during a conversation. In other words, patterns of change in the fundamental frequency in a voice of a person are analyzed, and the degree of emotions, such as "calm," "anger," "joy," "sorrow," and "excitement," included in the voice is determined. MIMOSYS produces a value for "vitality," which quantifies the mental state at the time of the conversation based on emotions analyzed by ST. The value is between 0 and 1, where a higher value represents a healthier mental state.

The minimum unit of the voice analyzed by ST is an "utterance," which is a continuous voice separated by breaths. In reality, the beginning of an utterance is detected when the state changes from silence to an uttering state that continues for a certain period of time, and the end of an utterance is detected when the uttering state changes to silence that continues for a certain period. Whether the state is in a speaking state or a muted state is determined by treating the amplitudes of a time waveform of the voice as threshold values. In MIMOSYS, at least seven utterances are needed to achieve sufficient precision, and a vitality value is considered valid if it is calculated from seven or more utterances.

B. Vocal data

Sound corpus CENSREC-1-C [15], provided by the Speech Resources Consortium, was used to evaluate the precision of vitality. This corpus consists of simulation data where noise is added and the data is recorded

under an actual noisy environment. A single speech datum consists of speeches that read a series of numbers with a certain level of interval in between, and includes about 10 utterances. Simulated data include voices in a clean environment to which a noise is added, where the noise levels are defined by SNR in a -5–20 dB (5 dB increment) range for eight noisy environments, including a subway, the chatter of a crowd, inside a car, an exhibition hall, a restaurant, a roadway, an airport, and a train station. There are 104 speakers (52 each of males and females) across all noisy environments. Actual noisy environment data are recorded in a dining hall for students and near a highway, and feature speeches in two types of SNR environment (low and high). In a student dining hall, the crowded period is defined as a low SNR (69.7 dBA on average), and the quiet period as a high SNR (53.4 dBA on average). In the proximity of a highway, the point near the main lane is defined as a low SNR (69.2 dBA on average), and the point near the side road as a high SNR (58.4 dBA on average). For the actual environment, a microphone is placed near the speaker (headset) and at a distance (50 cm from the mouth of the speaker), and speech was recorded simultaneously. There are 10 speakers (5 males and 5 females) across all noisy environments.

C. Experiment

Fig. 1 shows the procedure for the evaluation experiment. First, speech data was converted to 11 kHz, 16 bit, 1 ch pulse-code modulation (PCM) data to enable vocal analysis by MIMOSYS. The format of the voices was converted using EcoDecoTooL version 1.14, a free software.

Fig. 1 Experimental procedure

Next, intervals other than vocal utterances were muted to obtain valid utterances for the analysis. Intervals were muted using labeled data, which are recordings of utterance intervals for each voice, contained in the sound corpus. Data in which vocal utterance intervals were muted was also prepared to investigate the vitality of the noises themselves. The dataset in which intervals other than an utterance were muted is called S, and the dataset in which utterance intervals are muted is called N.

The vitality was computed by MIMOSYS for these datasets. For simulation data, the vitality of a clean voice was treated as a reference for comparisons with the vitality of voices with noise. For data from an actual environment, the vitality of a voice recorded near a microphone was treated as a reference, for comparison with the vitality of voices recorded by a distant microphone.

III. RESULTS

A. Vitality of the original data

Figs. 2 and 3 show the results for original dataset where no data was muted [14].

Fig. 2 (a) Changes in vitality and (b) changes in the number of detected utterances of a simulated voice

against changes in noise level under various noise environments (partially altered from [14])

Fig. 3 (a) Changes in vitality and (b) changes in the number of detected utterances of an actual voice against changes in noise level under various noise environments (partially altered from [14])

For the simulation data, the vitality value at a 20 dB noise level was lower across all environments than the vitality in a clean environment, and vitality tended to increase as the noise level increased beyond 20 dB for five environments (inside a car, restaurant, road, airport, and train station) (Fig. 2(a)). For actual environment data, the vitality value was higher for voices recorded at a remote distance compared to the value for recording nearby for any of the combinations between the pair of environments and the pair of SNR environments (Fig. 3(a)). On the other hand, the precision of detection for utterances during the vocal analysis decreased significantly for noise levels above 20 dB in the simulation data (Fig. 2(b)), whereas a similar result was also obtained for data from an actual environment (Fig. 3(b)).

B. Vitality for utterance intervals

Next, Figs. 4 and 5 show the results for dataset S.

For the simulation data, vitality tended to decrease across all environments as the noise level increased, but it changed to an increasing trend once the noise exceeded a certain level (Fig. 4(a)). This increasing trend began once the noise level due to a crowd or in a

restaurant exceeded 10 dB; vitality changed gradually at noise levels in the 10–0 dB range, and the increasing trend intensified past 0 dB in an airport and a train station. Vitality tended to increase past a noise level of 5 dB for all other noise environments. For data from an actual environment, the vitality value for a voice recorded at a distance was less than that of a voice recorded in proximity across all combinations between the pair of environments and the pair of SNR environments (Fig. 5(a)). In contrast, utterances were generally detected correctly in a vocal analysis for both simulation data and the data from an actual environment (Fig. 4(b), Fig. 5(b)).

Fig. 4 (a) Changes in vitality and (b) changes in the number of detected utterances of a simulated voice of dataset S against changes in noise level under various noise environments

C. Vitality for noise intervals

Finally, Figs. 6 and 7 show the results for dataset N. Clean speech data from the simulation data in dataset N did not include any noise intervals, and therefore, vitality was not calculated for noise intervals.

For simulation data, no significant changes in vitality were observed with respect to changes in the noise level across all environments (Fig. 6(a)).

Fig. 5 (a) Changes in vitality and (b) changes in the number of detected utterances of an actual voice of dataset S against changes in noise level under various noise environments

Fig. 6 (a) Changes in vitality and (b) changes in the number of detected utterances of a simulated noise in dataset N against changes in noise level under various noise environments

Fig. 7 (a) Changes in vitality and (b) changes in the number of detected utterances of an actual noise in dataset N against changes in noise level under various noise environments

The average vitality for noise in each environment was 0.58 for a subway, 0.60 for a crowd, 0.62 inside a car, 0.52 in an exhibition hall, 0.57 in a restaurant, 0.61 in a street, 0.56 in an airport, and 0.61 in a train station. For data from an actual environment, no significant changes in vitality were observed between voices recorded at a distance and in proximity of the microphone for any of the combinations between the pairs of actual environments and SNR environments (Fig. 7(a)). However, noise intervals during vocal analysis were generally detected correctly for both simulation data and the data from an actual environment (Fig. 6(b), Fig. 7(b)).

IV. DISCUSSION

First, each speaker reads the row of numbers at a constant tone, and no differences in vitality due to emotional ups and downs among individuals were expected to be found.

In simulation data for the original dataset without muting treatment, the detection of utterances almost always failed at a noise level above 20 dB. Several noise intervals were detected across all environments for noise levels between 15 dB and 10 dB, where several utterances were detected as a single interval that included noise. Every interval was detected across all

environments when the noise level exceeded 5 dB. Therefore, the vocal analysis essentially analyzed the noise and suggested the possibility of a high vitality value for noise, but these values cannot be deemed valid values because a sufficient number of utterances were not computed and a judgment could not be made. The same can be said for the data from an actual environment, as a voice recorded at a distance is detected as a part of the noise interval.

In dataset S, where noise intervals were muted, utterance intervals alone were detected where utterances also included noise, and therefore the impact of noise was detected correctly. Because a sufficient number of utterances were detected for the analysis of both the simulated and actual environment data, this indicated that the measured vitality decreases when noise is included in utterances.

Vitality began to increase once the noise level exceeded 5 dB in the subway, car, exhibition hall, or roadway environments for simulation data from dataset S, but the ratio of noise in a detected utterance interval increased and the system was essentially analyzing the noise. Therefore, the vitality approximates the vitality value of the noise itself when the noise level exceeds 5 dB.

Vitality tended to increase from around a noise level of 10 dB for a crowd, restaurant, airport, or train station for simulation data in dataset S. In these environments, noise includes conversations by others, independent of the recorded speaker, as well as voices from public announcements, where these voices become a significant factor once the noise level increases. Therefore, vitality calculated under a loud noise level in these environments may be for these voices rather than against the noise itself. In other words, the vitality under a louder noise level in these environments reached a level closer to the vitality value for the clean voice. However, it is unknown why a similar trend was not observed in an exhibition hall, where voices of others were included in the recordings of the speaker. A similar trend was also expected for a low-SNR environment in a restaurant for data from an actual environment, but such a trend was not observed. The interpretation of these results will be considered in the future.

The analysis of dataset N, where utterance intervals were muted, also showed a relatively high vitality for mechanical noise and a low vitality value for noise where human voices were observed. Therefore, vitality inside the car and on the roadway in simulation data

was slightly higher on average than the vitality of 0.6 recorded for a clean voice, and the vitality in a crowd, exhibition hall, restaurant, airport, or train station was, on average, slightly lower than the vitality of 0.6 for the clean voice. Vitality for the data from an actual environment showed a similar tendency as that of the simulation data, where vitality near the highway was higher on average but the vitality in a restaurant was lower on average. However, a different tendency was shown for a subway environment based on the simulation data. The interpretation of this result will be considered in the future. Between datasets S and N, the latter showed a higher vitality value on average. This may be due to the duration of the detected vocal intervals. Noise intervals were longer than utterance intervals. The relationship between the duration of the analyzed intervals and vitality is also a point of future consideration.

V. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the impact of cases in which a noise is mixed with voices in MIMOSYS, a technology that computes mental health levels based on voices. The results showed that the presence of noise compromises the precision of utterance detection for analysis. The mental health level was computed to be lower when a noise was included in the analyzed speech. If the noise was a mechanical noise alone, the mental health level was computed to be higher. These findings may help mitigate the impact of noise by applying an appropriate filtering for voices with noise involved when the precision of utterance detection by MIMOSYS is improved.

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